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RA-2 High latitude data assimilation study

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ABSTRACT:

This project has evaluated the usefulness of high latitude altimeter data in a data assimilation system for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas. Within the project we have focused on reprocessing and gridding of high latitude altimeter data as well as the development and implementation of a sophisticated data assimilation method with a state of the art OGCM.

The OGCM used is based on the Miami Isopycnic Coordinated Ocean Model (MICOM) which is a state of the art 3-dimensional ocean circulation model including thermodynamics and a mixed layer which interacts with atmospheric forcing fields.

The assimilation scheme used is the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF), which is a sophisticated method where proper evolution of error statistics is taken into account. The method has been particularly developed for use with highly nonlinear models with large state spaces and it is a natural choice for meeting the objectives in this particular project.

Within the project the OGCM has been set up for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas on an orthogonal curvilinear grid, with enhanced resolution in the Gulf Stream extension and in the Nordic Seas. The model also includes the Arctic basin and has an ice model coupled to it. Thus, the model comprises a sophisticated system for modeling the circulation and climate in the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas.

A pilot assimilation experiment has been performed where altimeter data have been assimilated into MICOM using the EnKF. In this experiment we used a low resolution version of the model system for numerical efficiency. In addition to the assimilation of altimeter data we also implemented the possibility of assimilating sea surface temperature data. Results from the assimilation experiment have shown that the overall assimilation system works very well, and motivates a next phase of the project where the assimilation system is used with higher resolution to get a more realistic representation of the ocean circulation at the scales resolved by the altimeter data. Further, the possibility of real time operation of the system should be demonstrated.

The work described in this report was done under ESA contract. Responsibility for the content resides in the author or organisation that prepared it.

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Executive Summary

This project has evaluated the usefulness of high latitude altimeter data in a data assimilation system for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas. Within the project we have focused on reprocessing and gridding of high latitude altimeter data as well as the development and implementation of a sophisticated data assimilation method with a state of the art OGCM.

The reprocessing of the high latitude ERS altimeter data was performed by a scientist at NERSC (V.J. Haugen) in collaboration with Collecte Localisation Satellites (CLS) in Toulouse, during a two months visit during summer/fall 1998. Thus, the project has benefitted from interaction and supervision of experts at CLS (in particular Pierre Yves Le Traon) during the reprocessing of the altimeter data.

The OGCM used is based on the Miami Isopycnic Coordinated Ocean Model (MICOM) which is a state of the art 3-dimensional ocean circulation model including thermodynamics and a mixed layer which interacts with atmospheric forcing fields. The model uses potential density as the vertical coordinate. This provides a better representation and conservation of water masses in the ocean since it eliminates the false numerical mixing seen in traditional OGCM, and it is ideal for use in data assimilation experiments.

The assimilation scheme used is the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF), which is a sophisticated method where proper evolution of error statistics is taken into account. The method has been particularly developed for use with highly nonlinear models with large state spaces and it is a natural choice for meeting the objectives in this particular project.

Within the project the OGCM has been set up for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas on an orthogonal curvilinear grid, with enhanced resolution in the Gulf Stream extension and in the Nordic Seas. The model also includes the Arctic basin and has an ice model coupled to it. Thus, the model comprises a sophisticated system for modeling the circulation and climate in the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas.

A pilot assimilation experiment has been performed where altimeter data have been assimilated into MICOM using the EnKF. In this experiment we used a low resolution version of the model system for numerical efficiency. In addition to the assimilation of altimeter data we also implemented the possibility of assimilating sea surface temperature data. Results from the assimilation experiment have shown that the overall assimilation system works very well, and motivates a next phase of the project where the assimilation system is used with higher resolution to get a more realistic representation of the ocean circulation at the scales resolved by the altimeter data. Further, the possibility of real time operation of the system should be demonstrated.

A conclusion from this study is that the reprocessing of the high latitude altimeter data results in a product which better retains the variability on scales which previously were filtered away in the traditional gridding process. Further, the altimeter signal in the Nordic Seas is strong enough to impact on the circulation and is certainly useful for controlling the evolution of an OGCM through a data assimilation system. A further improvement is expected after the new geodic missions approved by ESA.

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1 Introduction

The overall objective of this investigation is:

To implement a prototype for assimilation of high latitudinal ERS and ENVISAT radar altimeter data into an OGCM for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas.

The project (first phase) involves the following tasks:

1. Processing, validation and interpretation of high latitude ERS altimeter data.
2. Intercomparison of model and data annual mean sea surface height (SSH) in preparation for the assimilation study.
3. Validation and intercomparison of circulation derived from model and data sea level anomaly (SLA).
4. Pilot assimilation experiment.

In the next section, a brief overview is given of the ocean circulation in the Nordic Seas. Thereafter, the reprocessing and analysis of the high latitude altimeter data are described in detail. The last part of the report presents the results of the pilot data assimilation experiment and data model intercomparison.

2 General circulation in the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas

The Greenland, Iceland and Norwegian Seas, or using the Nordic Seas as a short notation, provide the major link between the North Atlantic and the Arctic Ocean. The bottom topography strongly affects the circulation and the distribution of the water masses. In the Nordic Seas there are four major basins, the Norwegian, Lofoten, Greenland and Boreas Basins (Perry, 1986). The Norwegian Basin is the deepest. The floor lies between the 3200 m and 3600 m isobaths. The basin is bounded to the east by the Norwegian Continental Slope and the Vøring Plateau, to the west by the Iceland Plateau, to the south by the Iceland-Faroe Ridge and to the north by a narrow ridge linking Jan Mayen Island to the Vøring Plateau. The Lofoten Basin lies northeast of the Norwegian Basin and has a much shallower floor, 3200m. The Greenland Basin is approximately the shape and size of its neighbor the Lofoten Basin. The majority of the basin floor lies between the 3600 and 3700 m isobaths. The Boreas basin (77 N) is the smallest of the four. An overview of the major circulation patterns is given in Figure 1.

The eastern part of the Nordic Seas is dominated by the warm and saline water originating from the North Atlantic Current which enters the North Sea as a surface inflow through the Faroe–Shetland channel and partly also across the Iceland–Faroe ridge. The current continues as the Norwegian Atlantic Current (NAC) flowing along the Norwegian slope, with extensions to Spitsbergen as the West Spitsbergen Current, and to the Barents Sea as the North Cape Current, (Johannessen, 1986). Part of this extension of the NAC branches off into the Barents Sea. Another part follows the slope northwards to the Spitsbergen region, where it mixes with the colder, less saline Arctic surface water, sinks and continues as a subsurface current into the Arctic Ocean. This branch continues as a counter clockwise current in the Arctic Ocean and reflects back towards the Greenland-Spitsbergen passage. The NAC also, before entering the Arctic Ocean branches off westward into the East Greenland Current (EGC) where it underlies the Polar Water from 150 m to approximately 800 m. An independent branch of the NAC brings Atlantic water into the vicinity of Jan Mayen island from the southwest. An infrared satellite image is shown in Figure 2, which illustrates the strong mesoscale variability and meanders in the North Atlantic Current.

Figure 1: Schematic of surface circulation in the Nordic Seas as derived from Lagrangian drifter data. Thick arrows represents the strong flows with speeds in excess of 40 cm/s. the East Greenland Current is not depicted, since it was not sampled by the drifters due to the ice coverage. (Poulain *et al.*, 1996).

The Norwegian Coastal Current (NCC) flows northward along the west coast of Norway, originating primarily from the low salinity upper layer water in Skagerak as well as freshwater outflow from the fjords. The Atlantic water inflow branches into a northward and southward current about 62° N. In turn, a distinct temperature front and cyclonic current shear is formed along the front to the south. The two currents north of the branching point form a front maintained in both the salinity and temperature fields (see Figure 2). During winter the NCC is characterized by cold and fresh coastal water with temperature ranging from 2° to 5° C, and salinity less than 34.8 psu, while the Atlantic water has a temperature exceeding 6° C and salinity greater than 35 psu (Sætre and Ljøen, 1972). The stratification over the Haltenbanken is relatively weak during winter, which favors trapped anticyclonic vortex circulation (Eide, 1979). This vortex in turn produces considerable horizontal shear across the east slope where the flow encounters the opposing coastal current.

In the western part of the Nordic Seas one finds colder and fresher water masses. These are a mixture of water originating from the Arctic outflow through the Fram Strait which flows southward along the East Greenland coast as the East Greenland current, and cooled water from the North Atlantic Current which has recirculated in the Nordic Seas and lost heat to the atmosphere. The circulation in the Greenland Sea has been found to consist of a large cyclonic gyre which is caused by an eastward movement of part of the Polar Water from the EGC north of Jan Mayen, the Jan Mayen Polar Current, and a westward movement of part of the Atlantic water.

The East Greenland Current (EGC) flows southward along the East Greenland coast and consist mainly of water entering the Greenland Sea through the Fram strait. Comparison with bathymetry and circulation shows that the EGCs eastern boundary correlates well with the continental slope in the

Figure 2: Infra-red image from NOAA-6 on May 14, 1980, showing the Norwegian Atlantic Current (red, at a temperature of about 6°C) and its boundary with the Norwegian Coastal Current (blue at about 4°C). The image illustrates the eddy circulation, and the spatial scales of eddies and frontal meanders. Adapted from (Johannessen, 1986).

Data	Cycles	Time Range
ERS-1, phase C	6 to 8	October 6, 1992 to December 23, 1993
ERS-1, phase G	10 to 13	March 24 1995 to June 2, 1996
ERS-2, phase A	1 to 24	April 24, 1995 to September 1, 1997
Topex/Poseidon	11 to 158	January 1993 to January 1997

Table 1: Overview of the ERS orbit cycles used.

Greenland Sea. The current also transports a large quantity of Arctic ice southward along the East Greenland coast.

The East Icelandic Current flows southeastward, northeast of Iceland and, thus, closes a general cyclonic circulation in the Nordic Seas (Poulain *et al.*, 1996). The flow of the East Icelandic Current, north of Iceland is controlled by the continental slope.

Helland-Hansen and Nansen (1909) pointed out the existence of weaker cyclonic circulation patterns in the Norwegian and the Greenland Basins, and possible in the Iceland Plateau. This circulation is constrained by the Greenland and Iceland slopes, and also by the topographic ridges west and south of Jan Mayen (Haugan *et al.*, 1991). In the Boreas Basin, in the Fram Strait (78° – 81° N) Johannessen *et al.* (1987) showed that cyclonic eddies with a characteristic vertical depth of 1000 m and a typical diameter of 20–40 km dominate the area. Drifting buoys indicate orbital velocities up to 0.40 m/s, and eddy life time of at least 20–30 days. Several of the eddies were topographically trapped, while others which were primarily formed by combined baroclinic and barotropic instability, moved 10–15 km/d with the mean current.

Important mechanisms which determine the mesoscale ocean circulation includes barotropic and baroclinic instabilities in the extension of the NAC and the NCC, and interaction with topography (Ikeda *et al.*, 1989).

3 Data processing

The Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) altimeter data products (AVISO, 1997) were used for this study. The SLA data are generated from AVISO GDR-M products for Topex/Poseidon and from CERSAT OPRs for ERS altimeter data. The data have been corrected for instrumental errors, environmental perturbations, the sea state bias, tidal influence and the inverse barometer effect. The ERS data are fitted to the more precise T/P data using a global minimalization of ERS–T/P dual crossover differences (Le Traon, 1995, Traon and Ogor, 1997). This provides ERS orbits with accuracy similar to Topex/Poseidon orbits (2 cm rms). The ERS bias and any long-wavelength error are estimated simultaneously with the ERS orbit error and are induced in the ERS orbit error correction.

The value of sea surface height was calculated as the orbit minus the altimeter range and corrections. The SLA files are then generated from several corrected SSH files using the repeat track analysis method. For a given track and for each cycle, corrected data are resampled every 7 km using a cubic spline. Data are then recentered relatively to the mean (or to a given cycle) to give the SLA.

The study area for the ERS data is confined to 60° – 80° N and 20° W– 20° E. Three different ERS orbit cycles are used as indicated in Table 1. Phase G for ERS-1 is the tandem phase with ERS-2, phase A, cycles 1 to 10. The coverage of tracks for ERS in the study are can be seen in Figure 3. The processing and validation of high latitudinal data was done at CLS, Toulouse, France during a two months visit in summer/fall 1998 by V. J. Haugen.

For the assimilation experiment the gridded Sea Level Anomaly (SLA) altimeter data products were

Figure 3: ERS ground tracks in the study area.

used for the area south of 60° N. These data are available by CLS, and have been through the processing and correction steps as described above. The gridded SLA are obtained using an improved space/time objective analysis method which takes into account long wavelength errors (i.e. correlated noise). The method is described in Traon *et al.* (1998). The temporal correlation function is Gaussian with an e-folding time of 15 days outside the equator and 10 days within ± 5 degrees, and have a resolution of 0.25° by 0.25° .

4 Filtering

In order to reduce the altimetric noise, each SLA profile was low-pass filtered with a Lanczos linear along-track filter. Different cut-off wavelengths were applied to find the best filter, this included 21 km, 35 km, 49 km, 63 km, 84 km and 105 km. For the filter using a cut-off wavelength of 35 km, a filter range which includes 5 points on each side of the point in the filtering was chosen, and with a cut-off wavelength of 63 km this range was set to 9 points. Before low pass filtering a median filter using three points was applied. A minimum number of 20 points along each profile was required for the median filtering.

The total variance of SLA for each filter was calculated, and the variance at each geographical location for the different filters for the SLA and geostrophic velocity were plotted. The variance of the SLA for ERS data was reduced by 20 cm^2 , from 69 cm^2 to 49 cm^2 using a cut-off wavelength of 35 km. Using a cut-off wavelength of 105 km the variance was reduced by 25 cm^2 , from 69 cm^2 to 44 cm^2 . For the Topex/Poseidon data the variance was reduced by 6 cm^2 , from 77 cm^2 to 71 cm^2 using a cut-off wavelength of 35 km, and by 11 cm^2 from 77 cm^2 to 66 cm^2 using a filter with a cut-off wavelength of 105 km (Figure 4, left plot). When studying the effect of the filters on different geographical positions, filters with cut-off wavelengths of 21 and 35 km provides a fairly homogeneous filtering of the signal,

Figure 4: Difference of variance of SLA and Geostrophic Velocity. Note that for SLA the difference of variance is plotted for the no-filtered data minus the different filters, and for geostrophic velocity the difference in variance reduction is plotted for the maximum filter, 105 km, versus the other filters. The large difference between the ERS and Topex data is due to an additional preprocessing applied to the released Topex/Poseidon products.

with no significance in the high variability areas. Filters with larger cut-off wavelengths remove too much of the signal, especially in high variability areas (Figure 5, right plot).

The effect of the filtering on the geostrophic velocity, calculated from the slopes of the SLA, was also investigated (Figure 4). The difference of variance between the 105 km filter and the other filters were calculated, since we expect that the 105 km filter reduces most of the noise. When applying the filter using a 35 km cut-off wavelength for ERS, the variance was reduced by $790 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$, from $970 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ to $180 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$, and with a cut-off wavelength of 63 km it was reduced by $908 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$, from $970 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ to $62 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$. For Topex/Poseidon a 35 km filter reduced the signal by $440 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$, from $610 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ to $170 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$, and with a 63 km filter the variance was reduced by $548 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$, from $610 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ to $62 \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^2$ (Figure 6). The 63 km filter turned out to best represent the variance in the region, without removing too much of the signal.

The effect of the different filters on the SLA along track was also investigated. As expected it is clearly seen in Figure 7 how the highest filters smooth and reduce the anomaly signal more and more, and filter away the noise, as the cut-off length is increased. Thus we decided to use the following filters for the high latitude processing:

- Median 3 points and Lanczos filter with a cut-off wavelength of 35 km for ERS SLA.
- Median 3 points and Lanczos filter with a cut-off wavelength of 63 km for ERS geostrophic velocity.

5 Spectral analysis

Spectral analysis was used to study the mesoscale variability and its spatial scales in the North Atlantic and the Norwegian Sea. A larger area than the study area was extracted from the global data set to get tracks of the same length within the study area since this is needed for spectral analysis.

The along track wave number spectrum of the unfiltered SLA obtained for the whole study area (Figure 8), shows a noise level of around $300 \text{ cm}^2/(\text{cycle km})$ for wavelengths up to 60 km for the ERS data. The corresponding spectrum for Topex/Poseidon shows a noise level of $50 \text{ cm}^2/(\text{cycle km})$ for

Figure 5: Reduction of variance of SLA due to filtering.

Figure 6: Reduction of variance of geostrophic velocity due to filtering.

Figure 7: Effect of filters on SLA data, along tracks. The amplitude axis is from ± 0.40 m as indicated for the bottom curve in each plot.

wavelengths up to 60 km. This white noise corresponds to an RMS signal of around 4.7 cm for ERS, and 2 cm for Topex/Poseidon, which must therefore be removed before estimating ocean parameters. The white noise observed from the Topex/Poseidon spectrum is very small due to the fact that this noise is removed in the initial processing.

To describe the spatial scales for different parts of the North Atlantic and Nordic Seas, the area was divided into 12 boxes, 5° latitude by 10° longitude. The spatial scales in these boxes can be described from the mean wave number spectrums and corresponding auto-correlation functions for SLA and geostrophic velocities as derived from each group of 600 km long profiles. Profiles with less than 5 consecutive missing points were selected. The maximum number of points along the track was chosen to 90. Most of the ERS tracks in the area has 84 points. Tracks with less than 70 points were not used.

The wave number spectra (and corresponding auto-correlation functions) were calculated by averaging the tracks in each group and calculating a mean spectrum per group. The spectra were calculated along each height profile by Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), and a cosine bell taper to the first and last 10 %

Figure 8: Mean wave number spectras for ERS and T/P. (It this plot and all following spectral plots, a confidence interval of 90% is also given.)

of the profile was applied.

A first degree polynomial adjustment is performed to eliminate long-wavelength components, basically orbit related. The most commonly used technique to subtract the long-wavelength error is polynomial adjustment (zero, first or second degree) over distances of a few thousand km. The accuracy to which the polynomial can be estimated depends on the number of degrees of freedom, or the number of independent measurements. Given the mesoscale de-correlation scales, the number of degrees of freedom may be low and errors non-negligible. The number of degrees of freedom in this estimate is assumed to be equal to $2(1 + (NT - 1)/3)(1 + (NCY - 1)/3)$, where NT is the number of tracks used and NCY the number of cycles on each track. This assumes that one cycle in three is independent, and that one track in three is independent. The mean number of cycles are 11 for ERS, and the mean number of tracks are about 28 for ERS. For Topex/Poseidon Box 1 only have 3 tracks and Box 2 have 15 tracks. The mean number of cycles is 176.

Most spectrums are generally not significantly different (Figure 9). Between 20–40 km there is a high peak observed in all box areas. The slope seems to be close to k^{-1} in all the boxes, even in Box 5 where we know we have higher variability than for the rest of the region.

For comparison, the wave number spectra for energetic regions like the Gulf Stream (Traon and Rouquet, 1990) have slopes of around k^{-4} , which are close to the values given by the theory of quasi-geostrophic turbulence. In the western areas in the Gulf Stream the most likely explanation for the generation of eddy energy is the instability (barotropic or baroclinic) of the mean currents. In our study area we find slopes close to k^{-1} to $k^{-1.5}$, which could suggest that other dynamical processes such as wind forcing or bathymetry may be important here in addition to barotropic or baroclinic instabilities. The mean flow is also significantly weaker than in the Gulf Stream.

Figure 9: Mean wave number spectras for the box areas.

Figure 10: The effect of filtering.

The peak wavelengths corresponding to breaks in the slope of the spectrums and the shape of the spectrum for longer wavelengths are useful parameters for studying eddy dynamics. A break in the spectrum is observed at wavelengths of about 200 km. After the break observed in the spectrums we might have larger scale activities.

These spectrums are one-dimensional along the tracks for the across track component of the geostrophic velocity. Thus for a wavelength k^{-1} these spectrums in the along track direction contain contributions from all wavelengths shorter than k^{-1} whose wave number vector components along the satellite ground tracks are k^{-1} . The effect of the different filters on the spectrum in Box 1 is shown in Figure 10.

5.1 Small scale signal

The one day difference in SLA from ERS-1 and ERS-2 was used to calculate the mean spectra to observe the influence of small scale signals in the study area. An area in the Gulf Stream was also chosen (60–20° W, 30–50° N) for comparison.

The small scale signals seem to be low in the study area (Figure 11), meaning its contribution is not important for the mean spectrums calculated. The contribution of the small scale signal is higher during winter than summer, and also seems to be higher for the higher latitudes.

6 Auto-correlation functions.

The auto-correlation functions $C(r)/C(0)$, where $C(r)$ is the auto-covariance function obtained from the inverse Fourier transform, were calculated from the non-filtered data and the 35 km SLA filtered data.

Figure 11: Small scale spectrums for ESA study area (left) and Gulf Stream area (right).

Most of these functions show negative lobes which are partly due to the procedure used to remove orbit errors, and to the existence of opposite rotating (cyclonic versus anticyclonic) eddies. The zero crossing of the functions will be used to determine the spatial correlation of the ocean signal in the objective analysis.

The zero crossing values from the auto-correlation functions of the SLAs, which are of the order 140 km after filtering, indicate a superposition of large scale and mesoscale signals, as zero crossing values for the mesoscale signals are typically of the order 50–100 km. The zero crossing is observed to be around 140 km for the different boxes (Figure 12), and slightly higher in mid regions.

The geostrophic velocity calculated from the slope of the SLA have zero crossing values around 30 km after applying the Lanczos filter using a cut-off wavelength of 63 km. The large scale signals have been filtered away and we see that we get a zero crossing value for SLA which is approximately 3 times the zero crossing for geostrophic velocity which is of the order for mesoscale features (Figure 13). This is estimated from the fact that the covariance function for the velocity is the 2nd derivative of the covariance of sea level and given the chosen analytical representation, there is a factor of about 3.

7 Objective analysis

Conventional objective analysis (Bretherton *et al.*, 1976), when assuming un-correlated noise, only needs data in a small sub-domain around the point to be estimated. If correlated noise is taken into account, larger sub-domains are needed to properly distinguish between the ocean signal and this long wavelength error. Ideally one would need to select all the data in areas several thousands kilometers

Figure 12: Zero crossings of autocorrelation functions for SLA (left) and geostrophic velocity (right). ‘No’ is the zero crossing for the non-filtered data and ‘F’ is the zero crossing for the filtered data. For the southern boxes we differentiate between ERS and Topex data (e.g. Noers, Notp). Missing values in the boxes means there was no zero crossing in the autocorrelation function for that particular box. All numbers are given in km.

across. This is not possible because of the difficulty of inverting the covariance matrices. A specified method for selecting data has therefore been developed at CLS based on the following:

- Along track SLA data are smoothed to reduce measurement noise and sub-sampled. Only useful observations are kept.
- For each point to be estimated, data are initially selected in a large sub-domain, with typical radius of 1000–2000 km (space scale of long wavelength errors) and 10–20 days (time scale of oceanic signal).
- Among these selected points, all points within a small sub-domain with at least the size of typical space scales of ocean signals are retained. Outside the sub-domain only one in three to five points are kept.

The time influence for ERS is 18 days, meaning that when plots every 5 days are produced, the influence of the data 18 days before, and 18 days after this day is used to produce the gridded files. From the 5 days gridded plots from the objective analysis the temporal and spatial variation of SLA is observed. The output are gridded $0.2^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ SLA files, every 5 days. An example of gridded fields is given in Figure 14.

Figure 13: Autocorrelation functions after filtering.

Figure 14: SLA gridded 0.2×0.1 plots after objective interpolation. Examples are from March (left) and August (right). Due to presence of more ice in the winter, a larger region in the EGC is masked.

8 The Diadem model system

The ocean general circulation model (OGCM) used is based on the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM), originally developed by Rainer Bleck and coworkers at the University of Miami (Bleck *et al.*, 1992). The model is a full-blown OGCM containing a complete thermodynamics. It differs from

Figure 15: The model grid and bathymetry used in the Diadem2 model.

Figure 16: Surface temperature and circulation in the North Sea from the Diadem model, the third week of October 1997.

traditional models by the choice of vertical coordinate which is potential density. Clearly density can be a coordinate since it is a monotone function of depth and a unique transformation between depth and density in a stratified ocean exists. The model consists of a set of interior layers each having a constant density which mainly interact through hydrostatic pressure forces. The upper layer is a nonisopycnic mixed layer which allows the density to vary and which interacts with the atmospheric forcing fields. Thus, the transfer of wind stress, and heat and freshwater fluxes between the atmosphere and the ocean is accounted for in a realistic manner.

There is also an interaction between the layers taking into account the vertical processes in the ocean. The mixed layer will deepen in winter and retreat during summer. This leads to entrainment where the mixed layer imports water from the deeper layer in winter and detrainment where the mixed layer is depositing mixed layer water into the respective interior layers in summer. In addition convection is parameterized as a vertical mixing of the water column whenever the mixed layer becomes denser than the first interior layer with nonzero thickness. The mixing continues down through the layers until a stable stratification is obtained. Note that MICOM is one of a very few isopycnic OGCMs which allows for the interior layers to have zero thickness and to outcrop to the mixed layer or sea floor. In between the interior layers the MICOM model includes vertical diapycnal mixing of water masses.

The model is designed to conserve water-mass characteristics during very long time integrations (e.g. several 100 years). This is essential in realistic climate simulations where the water masses in the deep ocean need to be maintained with correct properties. The isopycnic framework provides complete control of the non-isopycnal mixing in the ocean, which is several orders of magnitude lower than the

Figure 17: Vertical sections of temperature and salinity taken across the Faroe-Iceland ridge.

along isopycnal mixing. In a traditional OGCM which uses either constant z -level coordinates or terrain following σ -level coordinates, one cannot completely distinguish between the isopycnal and diapycnal mixing, and strong numerical diapycnal mixing will tend to smooth the thermocline and destroy the vertical distribution of water masses. The standard picture of an isopycnal model shows the ventilation of the the mixed layer with the interior layers at northern latitudes through detrainment, entrainment and convection which gives rise to an advective transport within each interior layer of deep water formed at high latitudes to lower latitudes (Gao, 1998).

MICOM has certain properties that makes it ideal for use in a data assimilation system. The most important is that it allows for updating the vertical density profile solely by moving layer interfaces up or down, and without changing the T–S properties within each layer.

The model domain is shown in Figure 15. The use of an orthogonal curvilinear grid allows for the use of a large model domain where high resolution is still retained in the seas off Europe. The model grid is based on a mapping of the poles to two new locations on the earth. The mapping conserves orthogonality for all the grid cells which are all quadratic. The algorithm is presented in Bentsen *et al.* (1998). Since the southern model boundary is extending far south (approximately 50° S), the equatorial currents and the North Brazil current will be represented and feed water into the Gulf Stream. Further, by including the Arctic Ocean and a dynamic and thermodynamic ice model, a realistic interaction between the Nordic Seas and the Arctic is ensured. Thus, a proper representation of the inflow of Atlantic water into the Nordic Seas can be maintained.

This grid defines the Diadem2 model version which includes all of the Arctic and has a resolution of approximately 20–25 km all along the Gulf Stream extension and down to 10 km in the North Sea. In addition there is a Diadem1 model version with half of this resolution which has been used in this phase one project for numerical efficiency. An eventual follow-on phase will use Diadem2 for real time assimilation experiments, and a future operational system will have access to larger computers allowing a Diadem3 model with twice the resolution of Diadem2 to be used.

In Figure 16, the currents and the SST from the Diadem2 model are shown for the Atlantic Margin and the North Sea for the third week of October, 1997. Note the strong North Atlantic Current which transports warm saline water from the North Atlantic and also the Norwegian Coastal Current. The currents seen south of Iceland and the chaotic and energetic region south of the Faroes are also agreeing well with present knowledge of the system, (Hansen and Østerhus, 1999). Clearly the Diadem2 model does not have sufficient resolution to resolve all eddies and variability, although the general circulation patterns agree well with what has been previously observed. The model has been extensively validated in a number of other modeling projects funded by the European Commission and the Norwegian Research Council.

In Figure 17 vertical sections of temperature and salinity, taken across the Faroe–Iceland ridge, are shown to illustrate the sharp distinction of water masses which is possible using an isopycnic model. The figures shows the very cold ($< 0^\circ\text{C}$) and fresh deep water in the Nordic Seas and how it is separated from the warmer and saline North Atlantic water south of the ridge. Note also the dense overflow water along the bottom south of the ridge.

A traditional level model would require extremely high vertical resolution to provide the same pictures. The location of the vertical layers with constant density are moving in time according to the changes in the water masses. At locations where there are strong density gradients, there will always be high vertical resolution in the model. Thus, the use of potential density as the vertical coordinate resembles the use of an adaptive vertical grid.

Figure 18: Root Mean Square of SLA and geostrophic velocity.

9 Circulation derived from model and data sea level anomalies.

The root mean squares (RMS) of the SLA in the study area was calculated from the along track SLA after filtering and is shown in the left plot in Figure 18. The RMS values are generally low in the Nordic Seas compared to other high variability areas such as the Gulf Stream extension. The lowest values (less than 5 cm) are observed over the Iceland Sea/Plateau and the Vøring Plateau, while the most energetic areas are located along the path of the North Atlantic Current. In the Norwegian and Lofoten basins, high variability of around 13 cm² is observed, and also along the Norwegian coast. This high variability observed in the Norwegian Sea is as expected, due to the sharp turn in the bathymetry which leads to the generation of eddies and meanders. As an example Poulain *et al.* (1996) observed, using drifters, that many mesoscale rings and eddies are apparent in the Lofoten Basin with velocities of around 40 cm/s. For the RMS of geostrophic velocity which is shown in the right plot in Figure 18 values above 100 cm²/s² are significant. High variability is again, as expected, seen along the path of the North Atlantic Current.

The eddy kinetic energy have been plotted from the Diadem2 model and is shown in Figure 19. This is not exactly comparable with the RMS from the SLA data, but should indicate high model variability in the same areas as seen in the data. The model resolution is too coarse to properly represent the eddy variability in the Nordic Seas. The variability given by Diadem2 indicate similar areas of high variability as the observations, although it is lower in the model than for the observations. In Figure 20 the variability from a higher resolution (7 km) regional model for the Atlantic Margin is shown. This model is run in a nested mode with the Diadem2 model. Clearly with this resolution the model provides a significantly higher variability which is more in agreement with the observations. We expect that a resolution of about 4 km is needed in order to properly represent all the mesoscale activity in the Nordic

Figure 19: Eddy kinetic energy from the Diadem2 model.

Seas but this is presently not feasible in a sophisticated data assimilation system running on available computers.

Thus, the major result from the validation of the model and altimeter derived circulation is that both the Diadem1 and the Diadem2 models are too coarse for a direct intercomparison between data and model results. On the other hand, the models and observations provides similar locations for the high and low variability areas, and the large scale structures in the observations seems to match well with the model results during the assimilation experiment which will be discussed next.

10 Selecting an annual mean SSH for the assimilation experiment

When assimilating SLA data into an OGCM one needs to reference the data to a Mean Sea Surface Height (MSSH). In particular, the same MSSH should be used both for the SLA observations to compute SSH data, and when computing the model predicted SLA fields from model SSH. Several alternative MSSH data have been considered in this project. First, MSSH derived from altimeter data at CLS in Toulouse was used. This turned out to yield some problems since it still contains geoid errors, and these errors leads to non-physical updates of the model variables during the assimilation analyses. The best choice so far turned out to be to use the multiyear MSSH predicted by the Diadem2 model (see Figure 21). Even if it still contains some errors, in particular in the Gulf Steam extension, it leads to

Figure 20: Eddy kinetic energy from a high resolution (7 km) regional Atlantic Margin model.

an analysis which is consistent with the model physics. Significant errors in the MSSH might introduce false water masses and currents in the model, but when a model predicted MSSH is used these errors will be consistent with the model and should not cause numerical problems. The definition of an accurate geoid should still be considered as an essential problem for assimilation of altimeter data, and hopefully it will be resolved during the approved geodic mission (GOCE) planned ESA.

When the Diadem2 MSSH was chosen it could be formally proved that whether this mean SSH was added to the SLA data to provide real SSH data, or the mean SSH was subtracted from the model predicted SSH to provide model SLA data, identical results would be obtained from the assimilation analysis. Note also that SSH and SLA are diagnostic variables in MICOM, and the update of the full model state is based on computing the multivariate correlations between these variables and the rest of the model state. This will be further explained in the next section which describes the data assimilation method used.

11 The Ensemble Kalman filter

The development of new and practically usable assimilation techniques have progressed rapidly during the previous decade. Initially, the focus was on relatively simple assimilation techniques which were based on well known mathematical formulations, often originating from control theory. One example is the so called adjoint method which attempted to estimate a number of control variables such as initial conditions for the model and in some cases the forcing fields, by minimizing a variational penalty function.

Another popular approach was the Kalman Filter technique, which can be characterized as a sequen-

Figure 21: The annual average sea surface height calculated from a fine resolution version of MICOM (Diadem2) and interpolated to the Diadem1 grid.

tial in time state estimation method. It integrates a model state and its associated error covariance matrix forward in time. At times when there are observations available the model state and the observations are combined to form a new analyzed state estimate while taking into account the error statistics for the model state and the observations. The analysis provides a variance minimizing state estimate and an updated error covariance matrix describing the error statistics for the analysis. These are then used as an initial condition for the integration until next time observations are available.

These methods were shown to work very well with linear dynamical models, but normally failed when being applied with nonlinear dynamical models, e.g. Evensen (1992) and Miller *et al.* (1994). Further, the methods were originally designed for use with low-dimensional systems having only a few control variables to be estimated. Ocean models have typically $\mathcal{O}(10^6 - 10^9)$ unknowns which makes the full Kalman filter impossible to compute, even on the largest computer systems available today. This has motivated an intensive research on the development and formulation of new methodologies which can handle nonlinear dynamics and at the same time be computationally feasible. A few such methods have been developed recently. One example is the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) which was developed by Evensen (1994) and has since been applied with a number of highly nonlinear dynamical models, see e.g. Evensen and van Leeuwen (1996) who studied the Agulhas retroflection using Geosat altimeter data together with a quasi-geostrophic ocean circulation model, and Evensen (1997) who examined the properties of the method with chaotic dynamics. Within the current project the EnKF has been implemented with the MICOM model described above.

The Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) was proposed as an alternative to the traditional extended Kalman filter (EKF). It was shown that if the dynamical model is written as a stochastic differential equation, one can derive the Fokker–Planck equation for the time evolution of the probability density function which contains all the information about the prediction error statistics. The EnKF is a sequential data assimilation method where the error statistics are predicted by solving the Fokker–Planck equation using Monte–Carlo or ensemble integrations. By integrating an ensemble of model states forward in time it is possible to calculate statistical moments like mean and error covariances whenever such information is required. Thus, all the statistical information about the predicted model state which

are required at analysis times are contained in the ensemble.

In Evensen (1994) an analysis scheme was proposed where the traditional update equation used in the Kalman Filter (KF) is applied, except that the gain is calculated from the error covariances provided by the ensemble of model states. It was also illustrated that a new ensemble representing the analyzed state could be generated by updating each ensemble member individually using the same analysis equation.

The EnKF is attractive since it avoids many of the problems associated with the traditional extended Kalman filter, e.g., there is no closure problem as is introduced in the extended Kalman filter by neglecting contributions from higher order statistical moments in the error covariance evolution equation. It can also be computed at a much lower numerical cost since only a few hundred model states may be sufficient for reasonable statistical convergence. For practical ensemble sizes n , say $\mathcal{O}(100)$, the errors will be dominated by statistical noise, not by closure problems or unbounded error variance growth.

The practical implementation of the method can be illustrated by the following equation.

$$\mathbf{A}^a = \mathbf{A}^f + \frac{1}{n-1}(\mathbf{A}^f - \overline{\mathbf{A}^f})(\mathbf{A}^f - \overline{\mathbf{A}^f})^T \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{C}^{-1}(\mathbf{D} - \mathbf{H}\mathbf{A}^f). \quad (1)$$

Here the matrix \mathbf{A} contains in each column a separate model state or sample from the ensemble, with the superscripts ‘a’ and ‘f’ meaning respectively analysis and forecast. The overline means the ensemble average, thus in the expression $\mathbf{A}^f - \overline{\mathbf{A}^f}$ we get a matrix containing all of the ensemble members minus the ensemble mean. This matrix multiplied by the transpose of itself and divided by the number of ensemble members (minus one) defines the forecast error covariance matrix as computed from the ensemble. The matrix \mathbf{H} is the so called measurement operator, which relates the model state with the measurements. Thus, multiplying \mathbf{H} with a model state is equivalent to measuring the model state (or projecting the model state onto the measurement space). The matrix \mathbf{C} is the model error covariance matrix projected onto the measurement space (or locations), plus the measurement error covariance matrix, \mathbf{R} , describing the error statistics for the observations, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{1}{n-1} \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{A}^f - \overline{\mathbf{A}^f})(\mathbf{A}^f - \overline{\mathbf{A}^f})^T \mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}. \quad (2)$$

Finally, the last expression is the residual between a matrix, \mathbf{D} , containing perturbed copies of the observation vector in each column and each of the ensemble members (projected onto the measurement space).

To summarize, the EnKF integrates an ensemble of model states forward in time in between measurement times, where the equation (1) is solved for the analyzed ensemble. This new ensemble will have a mean which is the new best state estimated and defines a covariance matrix which represent the error statistics for the analysis. For a more detailed discussion of the analysis, see Burgers *et al.* (1998).

Essential when developing a data assimilation system for an OGCM is to estimate proper error statistics, since this determine the influence each observation will have on all the prognostic variables in the model. The analysis must be computed in a dynamically consistent manner where all model variables are updated simultaneously to maintain dynamical balance. If for instance the measured sea surface temperature is greater than the model predicted value, the model mixed layer temperature should be increased by the EnKF analysis scheme. Of course, the update should be smooth in space, and other model variables like the density, mixed layer depth and sea surface height must be updated accordingly in order to be consistent with the equation of state. All the information required for computing this multivariate analysis is available from the predicted ensemble statistics.

12 Pilot data assimilation experiment

In the data assimilation experiment to be discussed next, the Ensemble Kalman Filter has been used to assimilate SSH and SST data into the Diadem1 version of MICOM. The model was initialized by

Figure 22: Assimilation of the global SSH data for January 24, 1996, where the high latitude altimeter data have been excluded. The upper left plot shows the model prediction while the upper right plot is the result of the analysis. The observations are given in the lower left plot while the increment in SSH from the analysis is shown in the lower right plot.

output field from Diadem2 for October 1995. Then an initial ensemble of 250 model states was created by perturbing the locations of the layer interfaces in this initial state by adding smooth pseudo random fields with mean equal to zero and a prescribed covariance. Thus, all the initial ensemble model states have different stratifications. Next, the ensemble was spun up by integrating each ensemble member until the beginning of 1996, from which date the pilot data assimilation experiment was started. During the spin up period, model errors were simulated by adding a stochastic noise term to the atmospheric forcing fields. The numerical experiment have been designed and interpreted in order to examine the value of including the high latitude ERS data.

Note that this is the first assimilation experiment run with the system and there is still a significant amount of work left in tuning and calibrating the system. In particular the prior statistics for model and observation errors need a more elaborate examination. Thus, the purpose of this experiment is mostly to show that the overall assimilation system is running and ready for use in a next phase where the focus will be on calibrating and demonstrating the system for operational use.

Figure 23: Example from assimilation of SST data for January 24, 1996. Note that the first guess is the analysis from the assimilation of SSH data. The upper left plot shows the model prediction while the upper right plot is the result of the analysis. The observations are given in the lower left plot while the increment in SST from the analysis is shown in the lower right plot.

The altimeter data products have been separated into two data sets, the first is the gridded global SLA fields produced by CLS using ERS and Topex data, but leaving out the region covering the Nordic Seas. The second data set is the reprocessed high latitude altimeter data for the Nordic Seas which were described in the first part of this report. In addition to the altimeter products, we have also implemented the possibility of assimilating sea surface temperature data. In the data assimilation experiments we have used gridded SST products also produced by CLS.

The analysis have been separated into three steps, one for each of the three data sets. It is possible to assimilate the three data sets sequentially as long as the errors in the data sets are uncorrelated. This is certainly valid for SST and SSH, and mostly acceptable for the two SLA data sets. The following discussion focuses on the impact of the observations on one particular analysis computed for January 24, 1996. In the first analysis step the global SLA data, below 65° N, are assimilated. The second step is the assimilation of the SST data and finally the high latitude reprocessed SLA data from ERS are assimilated.

Figure 24: Increment in SST from assimilation of global SSH data (left) and the increment in SSH from assimilation of SST data (right). These plots illustrates the multivariate impact of the EnKF assimilation scheme.

In Figure 22 the results of the assimilation of the global altimeter data are illustrated. The upper left plot shows the model prediction while the upper right plot is the result of the analysis. The observations are given in the lower left plot while the increment in SSH from the analysis is shown in the lower right plot. Clearly, the model produces too high SSH values southwest of Iceland and too low SSH values in the southern part of the North Sea. The model data do not deviate that much from the observed data at lower latitudes, although there is much more variability in the data than this coarse resolution model. The major effects of the analysis occur in the southern North Sea where SSH has increased during the analysis. This can be more easily seen from the SSH increment plot. Note that when using the time mean SSH from Diadem2 to relate the model SSH and observed SLA, it is not possible to correct the mean path of the Gulf Stream by assimilating the SSH data.

After the assimilation of the global SSH data the resulting analysis have been used as a first guess for the assimilation of the SST data. The results from this experiment is shown in Figure 23. The upper left plot shows the SST forecast after the assimilation of SSH data and the upper right plot is the analysis after the assimilation of the SST data. The observed SST data are given in the lower left plot and the increment in the SST from the assimilation is given in the lower right plot. The major effect of the analysis is to shift the location of the Gulf Stream front slightly southwards. In addition there is a correction along the coast of West Africa which is probably an attempt to fix a poor model representation of the coastal upwelling in this coarse resolution model. The large and localized correction in the North Sea is a result of an error in the model fields which was introduced earlier in the assimilation experiment due to a programming mistake. The assimilation of SST data will fix this bit by bit over the next few assimilation cycles, and the same will be true when assimilating the high latitude altimeter data next.

In this experiment we also used a fairly low weight on the data to reduce the amplitude if the impact on the model state during the analysis. This was done as a precaution to avoid large non-physical corrections in some of the model variables. This is something which may occur since a Gaussian assumption has been made for the predicted ensemble statistics when computing the analysis from Equation 1. This also explains the fairly week updates in the central Atlantic where the observed SST obviously differs slightly from the predicted and analyzed SSTs.

The multivariate properties of the analysis scheme allows other model variables than the ones observed

Figure 25: Assimilation of the high latitude reprocessed SSH data for January 24, 1996. Here a zoomed in view is used for the Nordic Seas. The upper left plot shows the model prediction while the upper right plot is the result of the analysis. The observations are given in the lower left plot while the increment in SSH from the analysis is shown in the lower right plot.

to be updated, by using the covariance statistics between the model variables. In Figure 24 the left plot shows the increment in the model SST from assimilation of the global SSH data, while the right plot shows the increment in the model SSH from assimilation of the SST data. These multivariate updates ensures that the analyzed model state is in dynamical balance and ready for a continuous integration by the model.

Finally, the assimilation of high latitude ERS data has been performed. The high latitude data are given on the region 20° W to 20° E and 60° N to 80° N. In Figure 25 the results from the analysis is shown. The strongest update is for the erroneous model SSH anomaly (discussed above), which has almost vanished after the analysis. With a change of color scale we would also see that there are significant updates of a few centimeters along the path of the Norwegian Atlantic Current. Also the high variability area west of the Faroes are subject to strong updates. Obviously, the assimilation of high latitude ERS data results in an improved SSH estimate in the Nordic Seas.

13 Summary and future perspectives

This project has evaluated the usefulness of high latitude altimeter data in a data assimilation system for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas. Within the project we have focused on reprocessing and gridding of high latitude altimeter data as well as the development and implementation of a sophisticated data assimilation method with the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM) which is a state of the art OGCM. The model has been set up for the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas on an orthogonal curvilinear grid, with enhanced resolution in the Gulf Stream extension and in the Nordic Seas. The model also includes the Arctic basin and has an ice model coupled to it. Thus, the model comprises a sophisticated system for modeling the circulation and climate in the North Atlantic and the Nordic Seas.

A pilot assimilation experiment has been performed where altimeter data have been assimilated into MICOM using the EnKF. In this experiment we used a low resolution version of the model system for numerical efficiency. In addition to the assimilation of altimeter data we also implemented the possibility of assimilating sea surface temperature data. Results from the assimilation experiment have shown that the overall assimilation system works well, and motivates a next phase of the project. For an eventual next phase of the project, the following issues have been identified as major points that should be further investigated:

1. The higher resolution Diadem2 model should be used to better resolve the scales of the mesoscale variability.
2. An extensive calibration of the prescribed priors (statistics) for model and observation errors must be performed.
3. A longer hindcast data assimilation experiment should be used as a proof of concept for the system.
4. The real time operational capability of the system should be demonstrated.

In addition to the items described above, we have also a marine ecosystem model coupled to the Diadem models. A similar data assimilation system based on the EnKF is now being developed for this model, with the purpose of assimilating ocean color data. Thus, it would be natural to incorporate this part into the next phase or even a separate but related project. Finally, we have just started a new development of a data assimilation system for sea ice. This will probably be completed by the end of year 2000. Thus at that time we should have available a complete preoperational marine monitoring and prediction system which will use Envisat and Jason altimeter data, Envisat SST data and ocean color data, and Envisat ASAR and SSMI data for the ice data assimilation.

A final conclusion from this study is that the reprocessing of the high latitude ERS altimeter data results in a product which better retains the variability on scales which previously were filtered away in the traditional gridding process. Further, the altimeter signal in the Nordic Seas is strong enough to impact on the circulation and is certainly useful for controlling the evolution of an OGCM through a data assimilation system. Further improvement is expected after the new geodic mission (GOCE) approved by ESA.

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